

EVALUATION OF NGURORE TERTIARY VOLCANIC ROCKS FOR HIGHWAY PAVEMENTS AND CONCRETES, NORTHEASTERN NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

The evaluation of the volcanic rocks at Ngurore quarry for use in pavements and other concretes was carried out in order to discover the source of the incessant structural and road failures where this important resource was used in the area. The sieve analysis carried out on the coarse aggregates all fall within the British standard limits. The average aggregate crushing value (ACV) and the aggregate impact value (AIV) obtained from the evaluations is 28.7% and 29.5% respectively and are within the acceptable standard limits. The specific gravity and water absorption gave average values of 2.60 and 0.22% respectively while the flakiness index obtained from the analysis is 26.7%. The results from the series of analysis all suggest that the rocks are suitable for both asphaltic and structural use as reinforced concretes.

KEY WORDS: Aggregate, Pavement, Volcanics, Plugs, Basalts, Concrete.

INTRODUCTION

The Ngurore volcanics are part of the extensively distributed rocks in northeastern Nigeria, such as Biu and Longuda plateau basalts which have been described in detailed by Carter *et.al.* (1963). They noted that over 300 volcanic plugs are scattered in the area including Hossere, Kohi, Wuro Yanka, Ibarre, Fig.1. Majority of these plugs according to them are composed of fine grained olivine basalts. Others are euhedral or subhedral pyroxene phenocryst that consists of diopsidic augite. Their location in the Yola basin of the Upper Benue Trough was the only answer to the numerous needs of crushed aggregates for the growing construction industry in Yola, Numan and other neighbouring towns in the area. However several failures have been recorded on the pavements where this important resource was used. The aim of this study is to appraise the suitability of this material for road construction and other concrete works and make recommendations to other areas where these failures could be traced to.

GEOLOGY

The upper Benue Trough is the northern portion of the Benue rift structure that extends from the northern limit of the Niger Delta to the southern limit of the Chad basin in northeast (Adekeye and Ntekim, 2007). The trough originated as the failed arm of an RRR triple junction following the opening of the south Atlantic in the Cretaceous (Burke *et.al.*, 1971). Fitton (1987) however associated the Benue Rift with the Cameroun volcanic line (VL) and that the central axis of the rifted basin is lined with Tertiary magmatism such as Billiri phonolites, Longuda basalts, Ngurore basalts showing prominent columnar joints that intruded the Cretaceous sediments.

In the central part of the Yola basin, the rocks comprises of volcanic plugs of many different sizes and shapes. Majority of the volcanic plugs encountered in the Upper Benue Trough were found to be basaltic only a few are non basaltic. The main folds consist of series of parallel fold systems conforming roughly with the ENE-WSW, E-W and N-S trending faults of the Benue trough. Adekeye and Ntekim (2007).

MATERIALS AND PARAMETERS DETERMINED

Samples of different sizes of aggregates ranging from 3/4" (19.05mm), 1/2" (12.2mm), 3/8" (9.52mm) and Quarry dust were collected from the Ngurore quarry at Ngurore village along Yola-Numan road for sieve analysis, aggregate crushing value (ACV), specific gravity and bulk specific gravity, water absorption and flakiness index test.

Equipment used for this investigation are concrete crushing machine, aggregate impact machine, flakiness gauge, thermostatically controlled drying oven capable of maintaining temperature of 200°C, pycnometer, standard sieves for aggregates, measuring scale (20kg capacity) and stop watch.

Table 1: Sieve analysis of coarse aggregates based on BS 812-103.1 (1985)

-Total weight of dry sample = 2000gr.

-Size of aggregate = 3/4" (20.0mm)

BS sieve size	Weight retained	Percentage retained	Percentage passing	Specification limit
128mm	00	00	100	100
¾" (20.0mm)	228	11.4	88.6	85-100
½" (14.0mm)	1548	77.4	11.2	0-70
3/8" (10.0mm)	156	7.8	3.4	0-25
3/16" (5.0mm)	64	3.2	0.2	0-5
Passing	4	0.2		

Table 2: Sieve analysis for coarse aggregates based on BS 812-103.1 (1985)

-Total weight of dry sample = 1552gr.

-Size of Aggregate = 1/2" (14.0mm)

BS sieve size	Weight retained	Percentage retained	Percentage passing	Specification limit
¾" (20.0mm)	00	00	100	100
½" (14.0mm)	214	13.8	86.2	85-100
3/8" (10.0mm)	987	63.6	22.6	0-50
3/16" (5.0mm)	278	17.9	4.7	0-10
3/16" (5.0mm)	73	4.7		

Table 3: Determination of Aggregate Crushing Value (ACV). BS 812-110 (1990)

Test Number	Test 1	Test 2	Test 3
Total weight of sample (gr.) (A)	2750.0	2780.0	2801
Weight of material retained on 2.36mm sieve. (gr.)	1970.0	1980.0	1990.0
Weight of material passing 2.36mm sieve. (gr.) (B)	780.0	800.0	811.0
Aggregate crushing value (ACV).	28.4	28.8	29.0
Average	ACV=28.7%		

$$(ACV=B/A \times 100)$$

Table 4: Determination of Aggregate Impact Value (AIV). BS 812-112 (1990), BS 882-2 (1973)

Test Number	1	2
Number of Blows	15	15
Total weight of sample (A)	2694.0	2680.0
Weight of material passing 2.36mm sieve (B)	786.0	799.0
Weight of material retained on 2.36mm	1908.0	1881.0
Aggregate impact value	29.1	29.8
Average	29.5%	

$$(AIV=B/A \times 100)$$

Table5: Determination of Aggregate Bulk Densities. BS 812-110 (1973)

Aggregate size (inch)	Wt of container +Wt of sample	Wt. of container	Wt. of sample only	Bulk Density	Average
¾"	8567	5170	3397	1.47	1.48
	8573		3403	1.48	
1/2"	8433	5170	3263	1.42	1.43
	8467		3297	1.43	
3/8"	8365	5170	3195	1.39	1.39
	8342		3172	1.38	
Dust	8968	5170	3798	1.65	1.65
	8964		3794	1.65	
Stone base	9388	5170	4218	1.83	1.83
	9365		4195	1.82	

Volume of container=2305, Density = mass/volume

Table6: Specific gravity determination of coarse aggregates. BS 812-110 (1973)

Material	¾"		½"		3/8"		Dust	
	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
No. of Pycnometer	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
Mass of Pycnometer A	803.5	803.5	803.5	803.5	803.5	803.5	803.5	803.5
Mass of Pycnometer+ sample B	1888.5	1962.5	1399.0	1286.5	1337.8	1428.5	1678.0	1740.0
Mass of pycnometer+ sample+water C	2746.0	2789.5	2435.0	2364.5	2397.0	2457.5	2606.0	2644.0
Mass of Pycnometer + water only D	2070.5	2070.5	2070.5	2070.5	2070.5	2070.5	2070.5	2070.5
Specific Gravity B-A/(D-A)-(C-B)	2.65	2.63	2.58	2.56	2.57	2.63	2.58	2.56
Mean values of S.G.	2.64		2.57		2.60		2.58	

Table7: Determination for water absorption BS 812 Part 2. (1995)

S/No	Test Number	1	2	3
1	Weight of saturated surface of samole (gr.) A	2200	2392	2196
2	Weight of oven dried sample (gr.) B	2195	2387	2194
3	Weight of water, A-B (gr.)	5	5	5
4	Water absorption, A-B/B X100	0.227%	0.209%	0.228%
Average 0.221%				

Table 8: Flakiness index test for coarse aggregates. BS 812-105-1 (1989), BS 1201-2 (1973)

SIEVE SIZE		RETAINED BEFORE TEST		PASSING AFTER TEST	
PASSING	RETAINED	WEIGHT (gr)		WEIGHT (gr)	
1.5"	1" (25.4mm)				
(38.1mm)					
1" (25.4mm)	¾" (19.05mm)				
¾" (19.05mm)	½" (12.2mm)	162		42	
½" (12.2mm)	3/8" (9.52mm)	201		56	
3/8" (9.52mm)	¼" (6.35mm)	72		18	
TOTAL		435 (A)		116 (B)	

FLAKINESS INDEX = B/A ×100 =116/435 × 100 =26.7%

DISCUSSION

The purpose of sieve analysis for crushed aggregates is to determine their specified envelopes. Higher values for “voids in the mix” for asphaltic concretes are as a result of the inability of aggregates to fall within their specified limits. However the studied samples all fall within the standard envelopes (Tables 1 and 2).

The strength of either asphaltic or cement concrete depends largely on its ability to withstand crushing as a result of frictional forces. The British standard (BS) specification for aggregate crushing value ACV is ≤ 30%

for asphaltic concrete and $\leq 45\%$ for cement concretes. The aggregate impact value (AIV) also gives a relative measure of the resistance of an aggregate to sudden impact and serves as a complementary test to the crushing value of aggregates. The British standard also provides a limit of $\leq 30\%$ for basaltic rocks. The obtained value of 29.5% is acceptable for use in all concrete works as seen on Tables 3 and 4.

The specific and bulk specific gravities of the studied samples also fall within the specified limits of basaltic concretes as seen on Tables 5 and 6. Water absorption is another quality test which relates to the tendency of aggregates to absorb water due to the presence of microstructures and fibrous minerals. Based on the British standard specification, water absorption should be ≤ 1.0 for coarse aggregates. The samples studied are also within the specified limit (0.22%) Table 7.

Flakiness is the tendency of a rock to break along some plane of weakness or when they have a thickness (smallest dimension) of less than 0.6 of their mean sieve size. The flakiness index of an aggregate sample is found by separating the flaky particles and expressing their mass as a percentage of the mass of the sample tested. Aggregates suitable for concretes should be rounded, sub rounded or sub angular in order to achieve perfect interlocking of the particles and based on the British standard, flakiness index should be $\leq 30\%$ for 3/4" and 1/2" aggregates. The obtained value of 26.7% of the studied sample as presented on Table 8 satisfies the minimum requirement for use in either asphaltic or cement concrete works.

CONCLUSION

The basalts at Ngurore quarry are products of the Tertiary volcanic episodes which are related to the Cameroun volcanic line. Here the basalts intruded the entire sedimentary sequence in the area. Attainment of perfect asphaltic and cement concretes is a function of the quality of aggregates used hence the need for such study to be undertaken and brought to public domain. The present study revealed the suitability of the rocks for construction purposes. Pavements where the Ngurore basalts were used as reinforcement or for surface dressing and recorded failures should query the earth materials used like the sub-base and base- course

REFERENCES

- Adekeye J.I.D. and Ntekim E.E. (2007): The geochemistry and petrogenesis of basaltic rocks of the central part of yola Basin, upper benue trough, nigeria. *Continental Journal of Earth Sciences 1*: pp1-10.
- Burke, K.C., Dessauvage, T.F.J. and Whiteman, A.J. (1971): Opening of the gulf of guinea and geological history of the benue depression and niger delta. *Nature (Physical Sciences) 223*, pp 51-55.
- BS 882-2 (1973): Coarse and fine aggregate from natural sources. *Publication of BSI (London)*.
- BS 812-110 (1973): Method for sampling and testing mineral aggregates, sand and fillers, Part 1,2,3 and 4. *Publication of BSI (London)*.
- BS 812-103.1 (1985): Methods for determination of particle size distribution- sieve tests *Publication of BSI (London)*.
- BS 812-105.1 (1989): Methods for determination for particle shape- Flakiness index. *Publication of BSI (London)*.
- BS 812-110 (1990): Methods for determination of aggregate crushing value (ACV). *Publication of BSI (London)*.
- BS 812-112 (1990): Methods for the determination of aggregate impact value (AIV). *Publication of BSI (London)*.
- Carter, J.D., Barber, W., Tait, E.A. and Jones, J.P. (1963): The geology of parts of adamawa, bauchi and bornu provinces of northeastern Nigeria. *Bulletin Geological Survey of Nigeria 30*, pp1-109.
- Fitton, J.G. (1987); The Cameroun line, West Africa: A comparism between oceanic and continental alkaline volcanism. *Geological Society of London Special publications, 30*, pp273-291.

Received for Publication: 14/05/2011
Accepted for Publication: 05/07/2011

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